

Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 2,13-dimethyl-3,14-di-n-propyl-1,4,12,15-tetraazacyclodocosa-1,3,12,14-tetraene

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2+2 Cyclocondensation of 2,3-hexanedione with 1,7-diaminoheptane in the presence of metal ions as templates resulted in the formation of macrocyclic complexes of the types [ML(NO₃)₂NO₃] (M = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}), [ML(NO₃)₂] (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}), [CuL]Cl₂ and [ZnLCl₂] (L = 2,13-dimethyl-3,14-di-n-propyl-1,4,12,15-tetraazacyclodocosa-1,3,12,14-tetraene). These complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, electronic and IR spectra, conductance and magnetic measurements.

Due to their relevance with naturally occurring biomolecules, there has been growing interest in the recent years in the study of metal complexes of synthetic azamacrocycles¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our earlier work⁵ on tetraazamacrocycles, we report here the synthesis of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of a 22-membered tetraazamacrocyclic, 2,13-dimethyl-3,14-di-n-propyl-1,4,12,15-tetraazacyclodocosa-1,3,12,14-tetraene (L), derived from 2,3-hexanedione and 1,7-diaminoheptane.

Results and discussion

Metal complexes (I) of tetraazamacrocycles have been obtained by 1 : 2 : 2 molar reactions of metal salts with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,7-diaminoheptane (Scheme 1). The resulting macrocyclic complexes are coloured solids and stable at room temperature but decompose at higher temperature. These are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and methanol but are readily soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. The obtained elemental analysis of complexes confirm their stoichiometry (Table 1).

Eggleston and Jackels⁶ have ruled out the possibility of the formation of 1+1 condensation products, such as diazepine, during the template synthesis of Fe^{II}, Co^{III} and Ni^{II} complexes of 2,9-dimethyl-3,10-diphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene. 2+2 Condensation leads to the formation of macrocycle having 22-membered ring which can accommodate metal ions of smaller size than that of the macrocyclic ring due to greater flexibility, forming stable complexes⁷.

M	X	m	n	x
Cr	NO ₃	3	1	9
Fe	NO ₃	3	1	9
Co	NO ₃	2	0	6
Ni	NO ₃	2	0	6
Cu	Cl	2	2	2
Zn	Cl	2	0	0

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

The molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions in DMSO of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes behave as 3 : 1 electrolytes⁸. The conductance values for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes correspond to 2 : 1 electrolytes⁹ indicating that both the coordinated nitrate groups are replaced by the solvent molecules. The copper(II) complex also behaves as 2 : 1 electrolyte. The molar conductance value for zinc(II) complex is very low showing it to be nonelectrolyte.

The electronic spectrum of chromium(III) complex ex-

hibits bands at ~ 16530 , ~ 25000 and ~ 26700 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(a)$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g(b)$ or ${}^4B_{2g}$ and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transitions respectively¹⁰. The iron(III) complex shows three bands at ~ 13700 , ~ 16400 and ~ 25000 cm^{-1} , which may be due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$ transitions respectively¹⁰. Spectrum of cobalt(II) complex exhibits bands at ~ 11000 , ~ 16400 and ~ 19000 cm^{-1} due to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively¹¹. The nickel(II) complex shows bands at ~ 9800 , ~ 16400 and ~ 27000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively¹². The positions of these bands are consistent with the distorted octahedral geometry with D_{4h} symmetry. Copper(II) complex exhibits a characteristic band at ~ 16400 cm^{-1} due to ligand field transitions¹³. Thus Cu^{II} complex may possess square planar geometry. All the complexes show intense charge transfer bands around 29400 cm^{-1} .

Table I. Analytical and physical data of macrocyclic complexes*

Compd./ Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)	Cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
$[\text{CrL}(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$ Grey	214	7.82 (7.94)	96	4.08
$[\text{FeL}(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$ Brown	221	8.50 (8.48)	98	6.44
$[\text{CoL}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ Green	145	9.94 (9.82)	54	4.52
$[\text{NiL}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ Green	172	9.69 (9.79)	52	4.18
$[\text{CuL}]\text{Cl}_2$ Green	118	11.63 (11.52)	51	1.87
$[\text{ZnLCl}_2]$ White	191	11.99 (11.82)	17	Diamag.

*All the compounds gave satisfactory N and Cl analyses.

None of the complexes exhibits bands at ~ 1700 and $3200\text{--}3400$ cm^{-1} in the IR spectra which could be ascribed to uncoordinated $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ or $-\text{NH}_2$ group¹⁴. All the complexes show medium to strong intensity vibrations in the region $1590\text{--}1630$ cm^{-1} attributable to the coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ resulting through the condensation of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups of α -diketone with the $-\text{NH}_2$ groups of the aliphatic diamines⁶. Nitrate complexes show bands in the region $1380\text{--}1390$ and $815\text{--}825$ cm^{-1} due to ionic nitrate¹⁰ and bands at $1010\text{--}1040$ cm^{-1} can be assigned to coordinated nitrate groups. An appearance of bands at $1460\text{--}1550$ cm^{-1} confirms the monodentate coordination mode of the nitrate group^{15,16}. In the IR spectra of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, appearance of bands due to coordinated as well as ionic nitrate indicates that the nitrate groups are weakly coordinated.

The observed values of magnetic moments for the com-

plexes at room temperature (303 K) are given in Table I. For chromium(III) complex, the effective magnetic moment is 4.08 B.M. which is in accordance with the spin only value for three unpaired electrons and is consistent with essentially octahedral geometry for the chromium atom¹⁷. The Fe^{III} macrocyclic complex has magnetic moment 6.44 B.M., indicating the high spin state of Fe^{III} with octahedral geometry¹⁵. The μ_{eff} value for Co^{II} complex is 4.52 B.M. suggesting a high spin state of Co^{II} ¹¹. The μ_{eff} value of 4.18 B.M. for Ni^{II} complex indicates the presence of two unpaired electrons and the geometry may be distorted octahedral¹⁸. Higher values of magnetic moments for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes may be due to larger orbital contribution. The copper(II) macrocyclic complex has magnetic moment 1.87 B.M. indicating the presence of one unpaired electron¹⁹. Zinc(II) complex is diamagnetic.

¹H NMR spectrum of zinc(II) complex of the macrocycle (II) was recorded. The α -CH₂ protons of the amine residue give a triplet at δ 2.58 ppm due to the coupling with the β -CH₂ protons. The remaining methylene protons (β and others) of the amine residue give broad peak at δ 1.30 ppm. In macrocyclic precursor, 1,2,8,9-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazadohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione (KIM, III) the α -CH₂ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.63 ppm and β -CH₂ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm²⁰. The free macrocycle has not been isolated during the present investigations but it is expected to exhibit these peaks at almost the same position as reported for KIM. As compared to KIM, in Zn^{II} complex of the macrocycle, these peaks are observed at higher field. Thus highfield shift of these protons confirms the coordination of the nitrogen atoms of the macrocycle to the zinc atom. The CH_3 (^a) protons of the ketone residue give rise to a triplet at δ 0.87 ppm due to the

coupling with the CH₂^(b) protons of the ketone residue. The CH₂^(c) protons of *n*-propyl group give rise to a triplet at δ 1.89 ppm and the CH₃^(d) protons give a singlet at δ 1.77 ppm. The peaks due to the CH₂^(b) protons of the ketone residue merge with the peaks of CH₂ (β and others) protons of the amine residue.

Experimental

Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, ZnCl₂ (all Fluka), Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Merck), CuCl₂·2H₂O (B.D.H.), 2,3-hexanedione (Aldrich) and 1,7-diaminoheptane (Merck) were used as supplied. *n*-Butanol was distilled before use.

Chromium was determined volumetrically as potassium dichromate using diphenylamine indicator. Similarly, iron content was also determined in Fe^{III} complex as Fe^{II} after its reduction with stannous chloride. Copper was determined iodometrically using starch indicator. Cobalt, nickel and zinc were determined volumetrically by EDTA using xylenol orange indicator for cobalt and eriochrome black-T for nickel and zinc. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as AgCl. Conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were measured at room temperature by a 304 Systronics direct reading conductivity meter. Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Jasco-7800 UV-Vis spectrophotometer at Mohan Lal Sukhadia University, Udaipur. IR spectra (KBr) of the samples were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature using a Gouy balance at Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali, Rajasthan, using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as a calibrant. ¹H NMR spectrum (DMSO-*d*₆) was recorded on a Zeol FX 90 Q FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as a reference.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : To a solution of Cr(NO₃)₃·9H₂O (1.5 mmol in ~20 ml *n*-butanol), a solution of 2,3-hexanedione (3.0 mmol in ~15 ml *n*-butanol) was added with stirring. To this, a solution of 1,7-diaminoheptane (3.0 mmol in ~15 ml *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring and the stirring was continued for ~5 h. The resulting solid was washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Similarly, reactions of Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O and ZnCl₂ with 2,3-hexanedione and 1,7-diaminoheptane were carried out and the corresponding complexes were isolated (yields 42–62%).

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